

**VUNOKLANG MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL
OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY EDUCATION**
(Faculty of Education, Modibbo Adama University, Yola)

ISSN: 2276-8114

Available online at <https://vmjste.com.ng>

**SUSTAINABLE FUNDING OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION IN A CHALLENGED
ECONOMY IN NIGERIA**

Jimritu D. Medugu¹ and Richard O. Uguwadu²

¹Department of Electrical Technology Education, Modibbo Adama University, Yola

²Department of Environmental and Life Sciences, Modibbo Adama University, Yola

Corresponding Author: medugu@mau.edu.ng, +2347032915191

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15843890>

ABSTRACT

The paper examines the need for sustainable funding of entrepreneurship education in a challenged economy in Nigeria. This study stressed that, gone were the days' education was for getting white collar jobs after graduation, but the reality has now changed in the country. The rate of unemployment now is alarming and that the government can't find solution to it except through entrepreneurship education, which aims at creating jobs to individuals. The paper discusses the meaning of entrepreneur and entrepreneurship education, funding of education in a challenged/depressed economy, innovation for sustainable funding in tertiary education, challenges of entrepreneurship education, possible solutions to the identified challenges of entrepreneurship education in Nigeria. Recommendations among others include; there should be increase in the budget allocation to education sector. This increase should meet the internationally recommended benchmark to ensure adequate funding for all levels of education and the government should create a conducive environment for businesses by giving out soft loans and lowering taxes for small enterprise.

Keywords: Sustainable, Funding, Entrepreneurship, Education, Economy

INTRODUCTION

One of the spotlights in solving global problems especially unemployment is the development and inclusion of entrepreneurship skills in education system. The world of work makes skill acquisition relevant in the employment of youths and school leavers. In Nigeria and other countries in the world unemployment is growing steadily in the society. The dependence on crude oil particularly in Nigeria contributes to unemployment because acquisition of skills to be self-employed is reducing.

The word "entrepreneur" came from a French origin meaning go-between or between takers. This further mean entrepreneur is one who shifts economic resources out of an area of lower and into an area of higher productivity and greater yield. Looking at this definition, an entrepreneur is seen as a person who add value to the economic transformation to his community. Also, he looks for a need to respond to meet the need and use it as an economic opportunity. An entrepreneur therefore, is the force behind every successful innovativeness while the innovation itself is wealth. An entrepreneur itself does

not cause change but seek for it. He finds the change and transforms it to his own advantage (Esther, Folakemi & Adebunmi, 2024).

Entrepreneurship education on the other hand try to provide students with the knowledge, skill and motivation to encourage entrepreneurial success in a variety of settings (Wikipedia, 2022). The scope, nature and characteristics of entrepreneurship education is a rebranding education culture meant to guarantee a comprehensive educational system re-engineering arising from the obvious deficiencies of the existing education (Igbokwe-Ibeto et al., 2020). The main purpose is to quip the students with academic knowledge, requisite, skills of creativity, innovative and risk taking, ability to turn ideas into action and capacities needed in the world of work as well as the ability to plan and manage projects in order to achieve objectives. This type of education helps youth to realize their full human potentials and take their place in society as productive, responsible and democratic citizens.

According to Shobayo et al. (2023), entrepreneurship education prepares people especially the youth to be responsible, enterprising individuals who became entrepreneurs or entrepreneurial thinkers by immersing them in real life learning experience whereby they can take risk, manage result and learn from the outcome. It is therefore the type of educational training that could be given to the interested individuals both adults and students through workshops, classes and conferences, thereby learning the basic of ideas starting their own businesses and managing it well. Similarly, Igbokwe-Ibeto et al. (2020) defined entrepreneurship education as the type of education that quipped the learners with the knowledge and skills to desire, seek recognize and utilize available opportunity to do something new and create wealth for self and others and later contribute effectively to the society.

The NUC Benchmark (2018) for entrepreneurship education are as follows:

1. To nature entrepreneurship knowledge among students with the hope of creating greater economic and social value to the society.
2. To provide students with the required skills to develop viable enterprise those that are capable of competing in the global environment.
3. To provide students with training skills that will make them met the manpower needs of the society among others

Also the following terms have been operationally defined:

Sustainable funding: refers to funding (financing) that can continue or be continued for a longtime

Challenged economy: refers to economy (income) that is not favourable for example with high inflationary trends or depression economy

It is expected that, at the completion of the programme, graduates of the tertiary institutions would be able to set up their own businesses with a view to be self-employed and to contribute to the society economic wise. The present study is important because it would theoretically provide a better understanding of how entrepreneurship education affects sustainability and economic growth in Nigeria; this is necessary as the high rate of unemployment and poverty is alarming (Igbokwe-Ibeto et al., 2020).

FUNDING OF EDUCATION IN A CHALLENGED/DEPRESSED ECONOMY

Despite several calls from public that poor funding of education can have a damaging effect on developmental education of a nation, poor resource allocation to education sector remains unchanged. The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) specified that for educational system of developing nations to witness

stability at least 26% of such nation budget must be channelled to education sector (Ekaette, Owan & Agbo, 2019). In spite the UNESCO standard of 26% the yearly allocation of the Nigerian government towards financing its education seems to have fallen below this global benchmark. Consequently, this kind of budgeting system operating in Nigeria might fail to achieve the sustainable goal of entrepreneurship education, which is to provide job employment.

The daily dataphyte (2025) examines the trend of the Federal Government Budgetary allocations to the education sector in Nigeria between the period of 2015 and 2025, the outcome of showed generally low allocations that were far below the UNESCO recommended bench work. Between 2015 and 2025 Nigeria’s education budget allocation decreased from 10.75% to 5.21% of the National Budget of 2023, falling short of the UNESCO standard of at least,15 to 26%. However, government budget is usually, on education sector. There is no separate budget for each area of education, including entrepreneurship education.

Table 1: BUDGET

YEAR	ALLOCATION (%)	AMOUNT (₦)
2015	10.75	483.2bn
2016	7.92	490.3bn
2017	6.03	448.4bn
2018	7.14	651.2bn
2019	7.12	634.6bn
2020	5.78	607.0bn
2021	5.90	771.5bn
2022	5.39	923.8bn
2023	5.21	1.07trn
2024	5.52	1.59trn
*2025	5.47	2.52trn

Source: Budget office of the Federation-Dataphyte (2025)

Note: During his presentation, President Tinubu claimed that N3.5trn which is 7.30% of the budget is allocated to the education sector.

The goal of the Nigerian Government is to make education free at all levels, in addition to assistance from international and local development partners. Grants for research and other donor agencies. However, depending on the type of ownership of the institutions, the major sources of income through which education is funded are as follows:

1. Government/Proprietor Allocation
2. Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund)
3. Students’ fees/levies
4. Endowments
5. Grants
6. Internally Generated Revenue (IGR)

Fig 1: Sources of income to tertiary institutions (Obioma, 2023)

INNOVATION FOR SUSTAINABLE FUNDING IN TERTIARY EDUCATION

Innovation for sustainable funding of entrepreneurship education in a challenged economy therefore, refers to new ways of continuing the financing entrepreneurship education that is education for acquisition of skills for a long time in a depressed economy in Nigeria.

Going by the situation in Nigeria, the economy is not favourable with costing buying and selling with high inflation trends. Cost of living is high making it difficult for social services like education, health care and importation of goods and services necessary for life to reach every individual. Employment of school leavers has crumbled, so investment in education for students to be useful after graduation is no longer achieved the traditional method of obtaining jobs through white-collar has failed such that graduates no longer obtain employment in the civil service, industries/companies with their qualifications.

In a challenged economy of this nation where income and expenditure are characterized with high inflation and poverty alternative favourable method of income generation is recommended for life existence to occur. However, major sources listed above are still being used in funding education, entrepreneurship education inclusive, but innovation or newness for sustainable funding of the education in tertiary institutions may be possible by the following:

- i. through budgetary allocation to meet the UNESCO standard of at least 15% - 26%
- ii. by eliminating corruption in our system in funding and implementation of the budget
- iii. alumni of the institution should also contribute to the funding of education
- iv. introduction of new courses like artificial intelligence, could also contribute to funding of education

CHALLENGES OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION

Entrepreneurship education has been embraced by teachers, students and society a it is geared towards economic growth, job creation and increase public acceptance. However, despite the positive effects of entrepreneurship education, it posed some significant challenges. Ayodele (2006) in Esther et. al. (2024) holds that, there are some inhibiting factors hindering the growth of entrepreneurs in an environment like Nigeria which can discourage both teachers and students from entrepreneurship education. Social System refers to forces of custom, the rigidity of statutory dictation and the distrust of new ideas and of the exercise of intellectualism that are not compatible with experiment and innovation thereby denying

opportunities for creative facilities.

Lack of essential infrastructural facilities, such as electricity, water supply which add to the risk and uncertainty of new entrepreneurship ventures, hence adequacy of infrastructure determines a country's success in diversifying production, trade expansion, coping with population growth, reducing poverty and improving environmental conditions. Entrepreneurship is also hindered by technological backwardness, the technology employed foreign countries and it seems inappropriate. Entrepreneur is also constrained by extreme inequalities in the distribution of wealth, people who are already established are reluctant to save and venture into manufacturing undertaking.

Education plays crucial role in the development of entrepreneurship education, providing individuals with quality entrepreneurship education is one of the ways of ensuring high entrepreneurial participation in the national economy. This goes a long way to make good economy. Nigeria's education is too theoretical, bookish and white or blue-collar job oriented.

Lack of or inadequate finance or capital based has been identified to be one of the principal factors hindering the development of entrepreneurship in Nigeria. There seems to be very high positive relationship between finance and entrepreneurial development and economic development of a country. Lack or inadequate finance has been a major constraint facing entrepreneurial development.

Fear of failure: - the fear of failure to a large extent reduces the rate of which Nigerian youth embark on entrepreneurial activities mostly from people who have a humble background, risk taking is one of the qualities of an entrepreneur.

Lack of time and resources: Teachers fear of commercialism, blocking educational structures, assessment difficulties and lack of definitional clarity are some of the challenges educationists have encountered when trying to infuse entrepreneurship into education.

CONCLUSION

This study has clearly shown the importance of entrepreneurship education to a developing nation like Nigeria. Entrepreneurship education is considered necessary to a dynamic economy, this is because it creates employment opportunities for the entrepreneur and for others as well. Despite the positive effects of entrepreneurship education, lack of infrastructural facilities, lack or inadequate finance or capital, forces of custom, has been identified to be among factors, hindering development of entrepreneurship in Nigeria. In addition to these factors, lack of quality education as a result of underfunding is a cog in the wheel of attainment of sustainable entrepreneurship education. The paper recommends among others, that there should be increase in the budget allocation to education sector, to meet the internationally recommended benchmark to ensure adequate funding for all levels of education.

RECOMMENDATIONS/SOLUTIONS

Based on the discourse, the following recommendations/solutions are proffered:

- i. There should be increase in the budget allocation to education sector. This increase should meet the internationally recommended benchmark to ensure adequate funding for all levels of education, including entrepreneurship education.
- ii. There should be a sustainable funding mechanism, this would establish a stable and sustainable funding for education that would be insulated from economic fluctuations.
- iii. Government should ensure implementation of transparent financial management systems and robust accountability measures to be employed to curb corruption and misallocation of educational resources.

- iv. Prioritize in-service training and professional development programs for teachers particularly at tertiary level.
- v. Visit infrastructure development, plan to address inadequacies in school facilities, particularly in laboratories. This can be done using innovative financing approaches like public-private partnership.
- vi. Continuously update the curriculum to align with the global best practices and emphasized entrepreneurial skills and creativity.
- vii. Promoting girl's education by addressing cultural and social barriers. This will include providing scholarship and ensuring safe and inclusive learning environment.
- viii. The government should come up with internship programmes for entrepreneurs that would pair students with prosperous business owners.
- ix. The government should create a conducive environment for businesses by giving out soft loans and lowering taxes for small enterprise.

REFERENCES

- Ayodele, J. B. (2006). Obstacles for entrepreneurship development in Nigeria in introduction to entrepreneurship development in Nigeria eds. The University of Ado-Ekiti press ISBN:978 – 812 – 09 – 3
- Bamiro, O. A. (2012). Sustainable financing of Higher education in Nigeria: Funding Models. Paper presented at the two-day consultative policy Dialogue by the committee of Vice-Chancellors (CVC) and Trust Africa, a Dakar-Senegal based HE Development partner on the theme: “the future and relevance of Nigerian Universities and other tertiary institutions towards Higher Education Transformation
- Dataphyte (2025). Daily budget card. Budget office of the Federation
- Ekaette, V. I. & Agbo, D. I. (2019). External debts and financing of education in Nigeria from 1988 – 2018: implication for effective educational management. *Journal of Educational Realities (JERA)*, 9 (1), 55 – 68
- Igbkwe-Ibeto, C.J. Mac-Ozigbo, A. & Osakade (2020) Effect of sustainable entrepreneurship education on career and aspirations of students of selected tertiary institutions in Anambra State, Nigeria. *Journal of Sustainable Development in Africa*, 22(10), 66-71
- Esther, O. A. Folakemi, O. M. & Adebunmi, A. O. (2024). Entrepreneurship Education for sustainable knowledge based economy National university commission (2018). Curriculum Benchmark, Abuja
- Obioma, N.C (2023). A new Dawn for Education strategies for sustainable funding in Nigeria. *International Journal of Social Sciences*, 6(4), 229-235
- Shobayo, M.A., & Ajayi, O.S. (2023). Education for Sustainability Development in Nigeria: The expectation and Reality. *ACU Journal of Social Sciences*, 2(1), 1-13
- UNESCO (2015) Education for all 2000 – 2015. Achievements and challenges; EFA Global Monitoring Report, 2025, UNESCO Publishing, Paris, France
- Wikipedia (2022). Free encyclopedia. Accessed, on August 16, 2022